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THE POTENTIAL OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FIELD OF ECONOMICS OF GREEN ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract

The development of science and technology is an inevitable product of the era of artificial intelligence, and the continuous development of green environmental design⁴ is determined by the high-quality needs of human beings, as well as high-tech, eco-friendly, and sustainable design concepts that are determined by the passage of time. The business strategy of "Green Business" is one that is based on profitability through environmentally friendly operational processes. In modern business, with the help of artificial intelligence and its techniques, green thinking can permeate the entire product life cycle, from manufacturing plants, production lines, machines, products, to supply chains. It is well-known that the world is grappling with the challenges of climate change and the need to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. Artificial intelligence has proven to be a powerful tool that can help optimize energy consumption, reduce waste, and promote the use of renewable energy sources. This article examines the impact of artificial intelligence on green economic growth and its mechanism. Thanks to artificial intelligence, it is possible to optimize energy consumption in factories, buildings, and cities. Tools such as predictive maintenance and optimized consumption planning can

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⁴ Green environmental design involves various stages, including project planning, site inspection, data collection, information organization, and scheme selection, all within a continuous process of seeking solutions.

reduce energy consumption, minimizing its harmful impact on the environment. Therefore, according to the latest research focusing on the green industry, this paper aims to bring a new development perspective, including artificial intelligence.

Keywords: green production in agriculture, artificial intelligence, and green economic growth and environment.

1. Introduction

At the beginning of the third millennium, the ancient question of the relationship between humans and nature, society, and the environment has once again come to the forefront. The emergence of the digital economy and digital technologies such as artificial intelligence have provided new opportunities for the green development of businesses. Now is the era of artificial intelligence when technology has the potential to fundamentally change the nature of production and its business operations. Artificial intelligence can be used to address various future problems related to the environment, including climate change and predicting natural disasters. Many hazardous tasks, such as the collection of radioactive waste, will be taken over by artificial intelligence tools in the future. For this reason, it is essential for all companies to establish a technology-driven strategy. These strategies should never remain stagnant but should be dynamic and capable of adapting quickly to changes with the emergence of new technologies. Green artificial intelligence represents a new technology that makes the development of artificial intelligence more sustainable and offers possible solutions to the algorithms necessary for obtaining energy⁵.

Artificial intelligence, deep learning, neural networks, synthetic data, machine learning - all these technologies have tremendous potential to revolutionize everyday processes and industries, including agriculture and society, leading humanity into an era of greater self-sufficiency and productivity. Green artificial intelligence is a subset of

⁵ According to Sergey Vilov's work: "Recognizing Speech Language on Mozilla Common Voice Audio Transformations," Green Artificial Intelligence will require data not only from computer scientists and mathematicians but also from cognitive science, cognitive psychology, neuroscience, cultural psychology, and many other diverse fields. <https://towardsdatascience.com/what-would-a-green-ai-look-like-28d91aaff3be>

artificial intelligence that is also focused on the environment. Green artificial intelligence requires specialized expertise in both artificial intelligence and environmental science. Its goal is to achieve sustainability through ecologically stable artificial intelligence models with lower computational costs and reduced carbon emissions. Societies worldwide must quickly recognize the value of green artificial intelligence in combating the growing environmental damage caused by current technology.

The central idea presented in this work reflects a significant area of application for artificial intelligence and the possibilities it offers for environmental protection, nature preservation, and the fight against climate change. Green artificial intelligence pertains to the use of artificial intelligence technology to reduce the impact of human activities on the environment. The environment is at the forefront of many companies' concerns, leading to a high demand for "green technology". Using artificial intelligence to manage the environment also raises ethical questions. In the long term, artificial intelligence will play a more substantial role in promoting green economic growth. Green artificial intelligence demonstrates its advantages that can significantly aid in mitigating climate change and promoting sustainability.

Green artificial intelligence must be effective for all relevant stakeholders in the economy, rather than being an abstract concept for most technical experts. The concepts of green artificial intelligence are expected to grow and become more democratic. AI-based systems can improve crop yields, reduce water consumption, and optimize the use of fertilizers and pesticides. This is crucial for reducing the environmental impact of agriculture and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

The latest developments in artificial intelligence have begun with the launch of generative tools⁶ and artificial intelligence technologies⁷. The climate crisis has become a defining factor, thanks to the selective use of scientific input, redirecting markets and economies

⁶ Generative artificial intelligence is a new generation that has its roots in traditional artificial intelligence and machine learning.

⁷ Debrah, C. , Chan, APC and Darko, A. (2022). Artificial intelligence in green building Automation in Construction, 137, [104192]. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104192>

toward green production and consumption to reduce carbon emissions.

2. Green production in agriculture

Agriculture is the primary occupation in many countries around the world, and with an increasing global population projected to grow from 7.5 billion to 9.7 billion by 2050⁸, there will be greater pressure on land resources. By 2050, there will be only an additional 4% of land available for cultivation. AI-based systems can improve crop yields, reduce water consumption, and optimize fertilizer use. This is crucial for reducing the environmental impact of agriculture and promoting fairly sustainable agricultural practices. Artificial intelligence is rapidly changing the way we interact with the environment and manage agriculture. The solutions addressing these issues are powered by artificial intelligence, which will enable farmers to enhance efficiency and improve the quantity, quality, and faster market availability of crops.

Agricultural production generates thousands of data points related to temperature, soil, water usage, weather conditions, and more. With the help of artificial intelligence and machine learning models, these data are leveraged in real-time to gain valuable insights such as choosing the right time for seed planting, determining crop selection, selecting hybrid seeds for higher yields, and more. Regenerative agriculture is rapidly transforming agricultural production due to numerous ecological benefits and productivity-related advantages.

Agricultural production is characterized as a labour-intensive activity. However, it is evident that there are fewer workers involved in it. Labor shortages, increased consumer demand, and high production costs are some of the key factors that have accelerated the use of robotics in this sector, aiming to reduce costs and optimize production. This has been the driving force behind the application of robotics in agriculture, which has significantly advanced over the last five years.

The goal of agricultural robotics is to enhance the efficiency and profitability of processes within the sector. In other words, mobile robotics work in the agricultural sector to improve productivity, specialization, and ecological sustainability. Agricultural robotics, for example, can precisely apply pesticides only to plants that need them. This is just one example of how very tangible benefits can be

⁸ Quoted from the source: <https://www.un.org/en/sections/issues-depth/population/>

seen in sectors that traditionally were not highly automated⁹. Agricultural robots can harvest apples, pick strawberries, harvest lettuce, and weed crops. Additionally, in agriculture, dynamic work cells are being introduced where a single human worker is assisted by several robots equipped with artificial intelligence algorithms and intelligent sensors in various stages of fruit production.

Drones¹⁰ powered by artificial intelligence are used for weed control, as they can detect and spray only the weeds, ensuring the protection of crops from chemicals. This offers farmers a cost-effective way to incorporate technology into crop maintenance while increasing the efficiency of weed control methods. Additionally, drones capture aerial images that help farmers quickly assess the health of their crops. Furthermore, by using cameras and AI-powered drones, it is possible to monitor and manage wild animal populations more effectively. Aerial images can save farmers a lot of time by providing them with a bird's-eye view of their crops. This allows them to quickly assess vegetation health, insect issues, irrigation schedules, and weed growth.

Modern research has discovered the potential of using drones and cameras to achieve the concept of green production, which involves numerous climate variables such as temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity. A new formula called the Osama formula¹¹, has been developed for evaluating soil thermal resistance and overall heat loss, taking environmental changes into account. Moreover, modern machinery uses sensor fusion, machine vision, and artificial intelligence models to identify fruit locations for harvesting and assist in selecting high-quality produce. Artificial intelligence can enable farmers to reduce the use of fertilizers and pesticides, resulting in healthier crops and less environmental pollution. Additionally, AI-driven forest management can ensure sustainable forestry with minimal impact on the surrounding ecosystem.

Since artificial intelligence holds strategically important data about the environment and agriculture, it is crucial that these data are protected from unauthorized access and theft. Governments and

⁹ From: <https://robotnik-eu.translate.google.com/robotics-applications-in-agriculture/>

¹⁰ Precision AI's current effort is to bridge two emerging technologies, drone technology, and green technology, which are yet to become popular in Canada.

¹¹ The invention and formula (Osama formula) provide a method for evaluating R-values (thermal resistance) that prescribe an optimal energy system for constructing agricultural buildings.

organizations need to implement robust security measures to safeguard this data and maintain public trust.

3. The impact of artificial intelligence on the environment

The question arises: can artificial intelligence help in protecting the environment and combating climate change? The impact of artificial intelligence on the environment is a crucial factor, whether it is positive or negative, that must be considered. The most significant advantage of artificial intelligence is its ability to optimize energy consumption and reduce waste. Within the field of artificial intelligence, specifically machine learning¹², data from smart grids can be analysed to optimize energy consumption in real-time, reducing the need for energy production based on fossil fuels. This can lead to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to mitigating the effects of climate change. However, the application of artificial intelligence also raises two sets of issues when considering climate change: the potential exacerbation of social and ethical challenges already associated with artificial intelligence and the contribution to climate change through greenhouse gas emissions from computationally intensive AI systems¹³. Green artificial intelligence represents an approach to continuous improvement aimed at reducing the impact of digital technologies on the environment, society, and the economy. To continue with the digital transformation of societies, it is increasingly important to think about a more sober, fair, and efficient approach to digital usage to minimize its environmental impact.

In transportation, artificial intelligence can determine route optimization and reduce fuel consumption, leading to lower carbon emissions and improved air quality in the environment. Furthermore, in terms of environmental management, artificial intelligence can design new materials with specific technical properties, such as increased strength or reduced weight, which can be applied in various technical systems, from construction to aviation. These materials can be produced from renewable sources, reducing

¹² Machine Learning (ML): Artificial General Intelligence is based on advanced machine learning techniques that enable machines to acquire knowledge, adapt, and improve their performance.

¹³ Artificial intelligence offers many opportunities to address a wide range of challenges related to climate change, but it also has an impact on climate change itself. Artificial intelligence emits CO₂, and it is also part of the solution to the climate crisis.

reliance on fossil fuels and minimizing the environmental impact of production and transportation. Technical improvements such as increased energy efficiency and reduced material usage alone will not be sufficient, and consideration must also be given to the consumption of digital technology. This means that developing artificial intelligence for the benefit of the environment is not the same as establishing environmentally and socially conscious AI systems.

Finally, there is concern about the ethical implications of using artificial intelligence for environmental management. Artificial intelligence algorithms are only as good as the data they are based on, and biases in that data can lead to biased decision-making. For example, if an AI algorithm is trained on data that prioritizes economic growth over environmental protection, it may make decisions that prioritize short-term economic gain over long-term environmental sustainability.

Artificial intelligence can be categorized into different types, primarily based on its capabilities and functional basis. There are generally two main divisions:

- **Narrow or Weak Artificial Intelligence:** This refers to AI systems designed for specific tasks or domains. These systems excel at performing a particular task, but their capabilities are limited to that task. They do not possess general intelligence or consciousness.
- **General or Strong Artificial Intelligence:** This is a theoretical form of AI that has the ability to understand, learn, and apply knowledge across a wide range of tasks, similar to human intelligence. General AI does not currently exist and is a subject of ongoing research and speculation.
- **Super Artificial Intelligence:** This is an even more advanced and theoretical form of AI that surpasses human intelligence in all aspects. It is capable of performing tasks that are currently inconceivable for humans¹⁴.

The types of artificial intelligence reveal more about the future development of this technology. These types serve as a foundation for visualizing what the future of artificial intelligence might look like, as AI is crucial for understanding how it will progress in the future. Different types of artificial intelligence work in different ways, which means it is necessary to understand these different types to see how

¹⁴Based on: Đorđe Nadrljanski, Mila Nadrljanski, Mira Pavlinović: Digital Maritime Business, College of Inspection and Personnel Management, Redak, Split 2021.

they differ from each other. To distinguish the extent to which AI applications can perform tasks, they are generally categorized into three types based on their capabilities, which are rooted in the ability to mimic human thinking. These types differ from each other and demonstrate a natural progression towards today's AI systems.

The rapidly evolving nature of artificial intelligence has resulted in numerous terms for different forms of AI that have been achieved so far and those that are being pursued. Additionally, not everyone agrees on what these terms refer to, which contributes to difficulties in understanding what artificial intelligence can and cannot do. It is crucial to have the ability to think ahead because the future of artificial intelligence is predetermined, primarily in its types that have been scientifically described up to today.

4. Artificial Narrow Intelligence

The idea behind Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI)¹⁵ is based on the belief that the functioning of the human brain, by creating the right connections, can be imitated using silicon and conductors (wires) as neurons and dendrites.

The human brain consists of 86 billion nerve cells called neurons. These neurons are connected to each other through thousands of axons. Inputs from the external environment or sensory organs are received by dendrites. These inputs generate electrical impulses that quickly travel through the neural network. Neurons can then send a message to another neuron to solve a problem or not send it forward. Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI), also known as Weak Artificial Intelligence or Narrow AI, is the only type of artificial intelligence that has been successfully realized to date. The name comes from the fact that such AI systems are explicitly designed for a single task. Narrow AI is goal-oriented and designed to perform specific tasks.

5. Conclusion

Artificial intelligence has the potential to offer solutions for recognizing and monitoring sources of CO₂, emissions, such as transportation, industrial production, and agricultural activities. Artificial intelligence provides significant opportunities for environmental protection, mitigating climate change, and preserving resources and biodiversity. There are many opportunities for artificial intelligence to help various fields of science and the economy, some

¹⁵ Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI)

of which are focused on the ability of AI algorithms to recognize and identify objects using cameras and other sensors.

While there is enormous potential for artificial intelligence to be a "driver" for positive change, it also raises questions about fairness, interpretability, privacy, and security in all systems. Climate change is very real, and if action is not taken now, it may be too late to correct its effects. Innovations based on artificial intelligence can promote sustainable consumption, accelerate the spread of renewable energy sources, detect marine plastic waste, or facilitate the transition to sustainable transportation.

Green technology, as environmental technology, encompasses technologies designed to reduce human impact on the environment and promote sustainability. It covers a wide range of industries and products, including renewable energy sources such as solar energy, wind, and hydro energy, green building materials and practices, and waste reduction technologies such as recycling and composting systems.

Although the potential of artificial intelligence is undeniable, it must be managed and adapted to global climate efforts. By applying artificial intelligence to renewable energy sources, food sustainability, forest management, agriculture, and biodiversity conservation, it becomes a key player in the common quest for a sustainable future. The significance of rising global temperatures is evident as forest fires become more frequent, large forest areas are reduced, which has a degrading impact on wildlife, and leads to an increase in CO₂ levels in the atmosphere.

In conclusion, the potential impact of artificial intelligence on the environment is significant, both positive and negative. Artificial intelligence can enable companies to identify and reduce inefficiencies, optimize supply chains, and achieve sustainability goals. The perspective of artificial intelligence and green technology is a developmental perspective because it offers a way to address urgent environmental challenges while improving productivity, efficiency, and sustainability. Artificial intelligence has the potential to promote energy efficiency, waste reduction, and the enhancement of sustainable practices. However, it also has the potential to contribute to environmental degradation and the depletion of natural resources. It is crucial to take steps to mitigate the potential negative impacts of

artificial intelligence on the environment and promote responsible and sustainable use. By doing so, it can be argued that artificial intelligence contributes to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly future.

Literature:

- Debrah, C., Chan, A.P.C., Darko, A. (2022). Artificial intelligence in green building. *Automation in construction*, 137, 104192, <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104192>>, accessed on September 16, 2023.
- Dongare, A. D., Kharde, R. R., & Kachare, A. D. (2012). Introduction to artificial neural network. *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT)*, 2(1), 189-194.
- Frederico Azevedo et al. (2009). Equal numbers of neuronal and nonneuronal cells make the human brain an isometrically scaled-up primate brain. *J. Comp. Neurol.*, 513, 532-541.
- Jay, R. (2021). Data for change. What Could a “Green AI” Look Like? What could an environmentally-friendly AI look like in the future? Towards Data Science, November 5, 2021, <<https://towardsdatascience.com/what-would-a-green-ai-look-like-28d91aaff3be> >, accessed on September 16, 2023.
- Nadrljanski, Đ., Nadrljanski, M., Pavlinović, M. (2021) Digital business in shipping, College of Inspection and Personnel Management, Split: Redak.
- National Newspapers (2008). Regulation on environmental protection information system (the original in the Croatian language: Uredba o informacijskom sustavu zaštite okoliša), <https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/clanci/sluzbeni/2008_06_68_2233.html>, accessed on September 16, 2023.
- Rawat, R., Goyal, H. R., & Sharma, S. (2023, March). Artificial Narrow Intelligence Techniques in Intelligent Digital Financial Inclusion System for Digital Society. In 2023 6th International Conference on Information Systems and Computer Networks (ISCON) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- Robotnik (2022). Robotics applications in agriculture. R&D, Robotic Applications, January 31, 2022, <<https://robotnik.eu/robotics-applications-in-agriculture/>>, accessed on September 16, 2023.
- United Nations (2023). GLOBAL ISSUES. Population, <<https://www.un.org/en/global-issues/population>> accessed on September 16, 2023.